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بلدية دبي
DUBAI MUNICIPALITY

ص.ب ٦٧ - دبي

تلفون : ٢١١٤٣

برقيا : بلدية

Ref: DM/ED/25/601/507
الرجع

Date 30th March, 1972 التاريخ

Andrew Williamson Esq,
15 St John's Street,
OXFORD

Dear Mr. Williamson,

David Philips has written to me from Muscat and enclosed a copy of your letter to him dated 13/2/1972. I am sorry that you have not been informed before of the decision taken by the Municipality on your application. This was due to a misunderstanding I had with David at an hurried meeting just before he left for Muscat.

We were very interested in your application but have decided with regret that the Municipality is unable at present to afford the expenditure on the salary of a high qualified person such as yourself and in addition provide the resources to enable you to investigate the archaeological material in the area.

We hope the delay in replying has not caused you undue inconvenience.

Yours faithfully,

J. D. DARRY
MUNICIPAL ENGINEER

cc : Director.